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Abstract Book

Do Agroecological Approaches Boost Functional Biodiversity And Natural Pest Control In Tomato Crop?

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Agroecological farming practices aim to achieve effective pest control by fostering biodiversity, which supports the conservation of natural enemies. In this study, we compare the functional biodiversity within two open-field tomato crops with distinct farming approaches—one following conventional practices and the other agroecological practices—over two consecutive years. The agroecological approach was implemented at the Aristotle University Farm, where we established a tomato crop with two distinct plots, each bordered by flower margins sown with *Phacelia tanacetifolia* and *Fagopyrum esculentum*, along with soil application of the beneficial fungus *Trichoderma harzianum* T22. The conventional tomato crop was located approximately 15 km away. Throughout the growing seasons, we monitored insect populations multiple times using Malaise traps and visual observations. Our focus was on wasps, hoverflies, and mirid bugs, examining differences in their abundance and diversity between the two cropping systems. Additionally, we assessed the population levels of key tomato pests, including *Tuta absoluta*, *Bemisia tabaci*, and *Tetranychus urticae*. Our findings support the sustainability of the agroecological approach, as it enhances natural pest control and crop productivity. Specifically, we observed higher species diversity and abundance, along with lower pest pressure, in the agroecological field compared to the conventional field. The goal of this project is to develop a model that can be easily adopted by small-scale tomato farmers in Mediterranean countries to protect and enhance functional biodiversity, enabling sustainable pest management.

Keywords: agroecology, parasitoids, predators, functional biodiversity, biological control

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